

Transport properties of the square-well fluid from molecular dynamics simulation

Iván M. Zerón,¹ Marina Cueto-Mora,¹ and Felipe J. Blas¹

Laboratorio de Simulación Molecular y Química Computacional, CIQSO-Centro de Investigación en Química Sostenible and Departamento de Ciencias Integradas, Universidad de Huelva, 21006 Huelva Spain

(*Electronic mail: felipe@uhu.es)

In this work, we have calculated self-diffusion and shear viscosity, two of the most important transport properties, of the spherical square-well (SW) fluid interacting with potential range $\lambda = 1.5 \sigma$. To this end, we have used a combination of molecular dynamics simulation and the continuous version of the square-well (CSW) intermolecular potential recently proposed by Zerón *et al.* [Mol. Phys. **116**, 3355 (2018)]. In addition to that, we have also determined a number of equilibrium properties, including internal energy, compressibility factor, radial distribution function, and coordination number. All the properties are evaluated in a wide range of temperatures and densities, including subcritical and supercritical thermodynamic conditions. Results obtained in this work show an excellent agreement with available data reported in the literature and demonstrate that the CSW intermolecular potential can be used in MD simulations to emulate SW transport properties with confidence.

Keywords: Square-well, Molecular Dynamics, transport properties, self-diffusion coefficient, shear viscosity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, the discontinuous square-well (SW) intermolecular potential has been used to describe interactions of simple, real and complex fluids¹⁻⁸ since it incorporates both repulsive and attractive interactions. Due to its simple mathematical form, multiple research have been carried out using perturbation theory⁹⁻²⁰ and molecular simulation mainly using Monte Carlo (MC) technique.²¹⁻⁴⁰ Particularly, many structural and equilibrium properties have been routinely evaluated including radial distribution function, coordination number, internal energy, compressibility factor, densities of coexistence, vapor pressure, surface tension, high temperature expansion coefficients of free energies, and chemical potential, among many others. Unfortunately, there exist a limited number of publications in which transport properties of systems that interact via discontinuous intermolecular potentials from computer simulation, including the SW fluid. Particularly relevant in this work is a series of works developed by Michels and Trappernier in the 80's.⁴¹⁻⁴⁶

The existence of few number studies dealing with transport properties of fluids that interact through discontinuous intermolecular potentials could be due to the combination of two main reasons. On the one hand, transport properties are almost impossible to be calculated via MC simulation since it is necessary the continuous trajectory of all particles over the time. And on the other hand, discontinuous potentials can not be studied through MD simulations since continuous forces are required to solve Newton's equation.

To overcome this problem, authors in the past have proposed two different ways. The first option is to modify the molecular dynamics algorithm itself. A suitable choice is to use the collision scheme, instead solving Newton equations, in which the energy and momentum are conserved quantities before and after of the collision.^{47,48} With this algorithm, the direct contact between particles is avoided and transport properties can be computed. This is the case of the works of Michels

and Trappernier. Unfortunately, the use of this technique is not widespread.

The second solution usually proposed is to perform standard MD simulations and modify the discontinuous potential to a soft version capable to reproduce all (or almost all) equilibrium and non-equilibrium properties by setting several free parameters.⁴⁹⁻⁵³ Examples of this approach are the soft version of the hard sphere⁵¹ and the CSW intermolecular potential recently proposed by Zerón *et al.*⁵² In this research, we adopt this last idea. According to this, the main goal of this work is to determine self-diffusion and shear viscosity, and several structural and thermodynamic properties of the SW fluid combining molecular dynamics simulations and the CSW intermolecular potential.

The organization of the paper is as follow: In Sec. II, we describe the methodology used in this work to estimate transport properties, particularly, self-diffusion coefficients and shear-viscosity using standard equilibrium MD simulations. Specific details related to the MD implementation can be found in Sec. III. The results obtained as well as their discussion, are described in Sec. IV. Finally, conclusions are presented in Sec. V. Numerical data of this work has been included as Supplementary Material.

II. TRANSPORT PROPERTIES BY COMPUTER SIMULATIONS

Transport phenomena involves the study of a number of properties in systems in which mass, energy, charge, momentum or angular momentum is exchanged. In MD simulations, there are two frameworks to calculate transport properties. In the first one, the system is in equilibrium. In the second one, the system is in non-equilibrium. In both cases, there exist well established formalisms and equations to compute them. For instance, the Green-Kubo integral equation and the Einstein differential formula are routinely used in the case of

equilibrium MD simulations.

Considering the view in which the system is in equilibrium, it is possible to express a given transport property in terms of a suitable correlation function of a dynamical magnitude. In the case of self-diffusion and the shear viscosity, the dynamic properties are related with the positions of the particles forming the system and the tensor pressure, respectively. We define both of them in the following sections.

A. Self-diffusion coefficient

The most common way to estimate the self-diffusion coefficient, D , is using the Einstein approach. In this case, the dynamic magnitude is directly related with the positions of the particles, as functions of time, and D is proportional to the slope of the mean-square displacement (MSD) at long times:

$$D = \frac{1}{6N} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d}{dt} \left\langle \sum_i^N [r_i(t) - r_i(0)]^2 \right\rangle \quad (1)$$

where $r_i(t)$ is the position of the i -particle at time t . Note that the ensemble average in Eq. (1) is taken for all N particles in the simulation.

B. Shear viscosity

The shear-viscosity, η , can be calculated with the well-known Green-Kubo formula:

$$\eta = \frac{V}{k_B T} \int_0^\infty \langle P_{\alpha\beta}(t_0) P_{\alpha\beta}(t_0 + t) \rangle_{t_0} dt, \quad (2)$$

where V is the volume of the system, k_B the Boltzmann constant, T the temperature, $\langle P_{\alpha\beta}(t_0) P_{\alpha\beta}(t_0 + t) \rangle_{t_0}$ is the auto-correlation function of the pressure tensor, which measure the rate at which the momentum in direction β is transferred along the α direction. The components of the pressure tensor, $P_{\alpha\beta}$, can be expressed as:

$$P_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{m}{V} \sum_{i=1}^N v_i^\alpha v_i^\beta + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N r_{ij}^\alpha f_{ij}^\beta \quad (3)$$

The first term is the kinetic contribution, being m the molecular mass, v_i^α the α component of the velocity of the particle i , \mathbf{v}_i . The second term is the intermolecular potential contribution, where r_{ij}^α is the β component of the intermolecular vector \mathbf{r}_{ij} between particles i and j , and f_{ij}^β is the α component of the vector force of j over i particle, \mathbf{f}_{ij} . In homogeneous isotropic systems $P_{\alpha\beta}$ is symmetric and η can be enhance averaging multiple terms from the stress tensor.

III. SIMULATION DETAILS

This study has been carried out implementing double precision MD simulation in the NVT ensemble using the well known GROMACS package.^{54,55}

To calculate all properties, we are using argon fluids interacting with the SW potential in its continuous version (CSW) proposed by Zerón *et al.*⁵² which mathematical form in reduced units is:

$$v_{CSW}(x) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\left(\frac{1}{x} \right)^n + \frac{1 - e^{-m(x-1)(x-\lambda)}}{1 + e^{-m(x-1)(x-\lambda)}} - 1 \right), \quad (4)$$

where the potential in function of the reduced distance $x = r/\sigma$ is defined as $v_{CSW}(x) = V_{CSW}(x)/\epsilon$, with the hard sphere diameter value taken as $\sigma = 0.3405$, the well energy $\epsilon = 0.996078$ kJ/mol, well range $\lambda = 1.5\sigma$, and the softness parameters $n = 2500$ and $m = 20000$ as its original value. The CSW potential and its derivative are provided to GROMACS in an input file where numerical values are tabulated each 0.0001 nm.

For all runs, we implemented simulations of 2ns long to equilibrate the system and 20 ns to average all properties. To solve dynamic equations the leap-frog integrator⁵⁶ is used with a time step of 0.1 fs, temperature was controlled in the interval of 80-600 K using the Nosé-Hoover thermostat^{57,58} with coupling constant $\tau = 2$ ps. We selected two system sizes: one with 108 argon atoms in order to compare CSW predictions of the transport properties with the only ones available, and other system with 1000 to produce new data for all properties. In both cases the atoms were randomly positioned in a cubic box with periodic boundary conditions applied in all directions and the densities studied encompass from 160 to 1450 Kg/m³.

The positions of all particles are saved each 50 steps, pressure components each 5 steps and no long-range corrections are applied due to we are using the same cut-off for the CSW potential implemented by the authors, it is, when $U_{CSW}(r_c) \approx 10^{-15}$ kJ/mol that for the case of range $\lambda = 1.5\sigma$ the cut-off is at $r_c = 0.512$ nm.

Results for all properties analyzed in this work will be presented in reduced units: density $\rho^* = \rho \sigma^3$, temperature $T^* = k_B T / \epsilon$, internal energy per particle $u^* = U / N k_B T$, pressure $P^* = P \sigma^3 / \epsilon$, compressibility factor $Z = P^* / (\rho^* T^*)$, self-diffusion coefficient $D^* = D \sqrt{m / (\sigma^2 k_B T)}$, shear-viscosity $\eta^* = \eta \sigma^2 / \sqrt{(m k_B T)}$.

IV. RESULTS

The performance of the CSW potential to reproduce the available simulation data for equilibrium properties in single and coexistence phase of SW liquid has been boarded in the original work of Zerón *et al.*⁵² In that work, internal energies, compressibility factors, radial distribution functions, densities of coexistence, vapor pressures, and surface tensions show an excellent agreement between CSW predictions and MC data reported by several authors for the spherical SW fluid. Nevertheless, transport properties have not been studied before using continuous version of the SW intermolecular potential.

With the purpose of showing that the CSW intermolecular potential can be used in standard MD simulations to correctly

FIG. 1. $T^* - \rho^*$ projection of the phase diagram of the SW fluid with range $\lambda = 1.5 \sigma$. The blue plus represent the thermodynamic states studied in this work, the black circles are the coexistence densities reported by several authors^{23,24,27,29,30,33,37} and the discontinuous red line separates the subcritical and supercritical regions of the phase diagram at the critical temperature.

predict the transport properties of the SW fluid, we have carried out simulations to determine self-diffusion coefficient and shear-viscosity of particles interacting via the CSW potential ($\lambda = 1.5 \sigma$) at subcritical and supercritical conditions, as indicated in Fig. 1. Most of the selected thermodynamic states correspond to those analyzed by Michels and Trappeniers.^{42,43,46}

Firstly, we compute the self-diffusion coefficients and shear-viscosity for a system formed by 108 particles. We then compare the MD results obtained for the CSW potential with values found by Michels and Trappeniers. Note that we have used the same system size than that of Michels and Trappeniers. We have also performed simulations, at the same thermodynamic conditions, but now using systems conformed with 1000 particles. This allows to analyze the effect of the number of molecules on both transport properties and also on equilibrium and structure properties.

To measure the ability of the CSW intermolecular potential in predicting transport, equilibrium, and structural properties of the SW potential, we also calculate the average absolute relative deviation (AAD%):

$$\text{AAD\%} = \frac{100}{n_t} \sum_{i=1}^{n_t} \left| \frac{X_i^{\text{CSW}} - X_i^{\text{SW}}}{X_i^{\text{SW}}} \right|, \quad (5)$$

where X_i^{CSW} and X_i^{SW} are the values of a magnitude calculated using the CSW potential via MD and using the true SW potential, respectively. Here n_t is the total number of simulation values.

A. Self-diffusion coefficient

To calculate self-diffusion coefficients we have performed several NVT simulations for systems with 108 particles inter-

FIG. 2. Self-diffusion coefficient D^* , as a function of density, ρ^* , of a system formed from 108 particles interacting with the CSW potential (filled circles), as obtained from MD simulations, and with the SW potential (open circles), taken from Michels and Trappeniers,⁴⁶ at several temperatures. In all cases, $\lambda = 1.5 \sigma$.

acting through the CSW intermolecular potential with range $\lambda = 1.5 \sigma$ at densities from $\rho^* = 0.025$ to 0.86 and in the range of temperatures $T^* = 0.6 - 5$. For each point studied, 5 independent simulations of 20 ns length have been run to determine the average value and to estimate the uncertainty associated to the self-diffusivity. The numerical value has been calculated using the Einstein relation of Eq. (1), i.e., we took one sixth of the slope of the linear fit applied to the 10 – 90% curve of the MSD in the diffusivity zone.

MD predictions found using the CSW intermolecular potential are plotted in Fig. 2. We have also included the self-diffusion coefficients reported by Michels and Trappeniers⁴⁶ for SW fluids. As can be seen, there is an excellent agreement between both values at all temperatures. Regarding all available data for the self-diffusivity, we found an AAD% between CSW and SW predictions of 3%, approximately. Notice that estimations obtained by Michels and Trappeniers were calculated using DMD and the Green-Kubo formula for a system with the same size and interacting via the true SW intermolecular potential.

At this point, we have shown that it is possible to mimic the diffusion of SW particles with the CSW intermolecular potential. Since the self-diffusivity depends on the system size, it would be advisable to perform several estimations with different number of molecules to extrapolate D to infinite limit ($N \rightarrow \infty$).⁵⁹ In practice, it requires a large quantity of simulations. Instead, we decided to calculate D also for a systems 1000 particles and apply the Yeh and Hummer⁶⁰ correction given by:

$$D_\infty = D_{sim} + \frac{k_B T \xi}{6 \pi \eta L}, \quad (6)$$

where D_∞ is the self-diffusivity in the infinite system, D_{sim} is

FIG. 3. Self-diffusion coefficient D^* , as a function of density, ρ^* , of a system formed from 1000 particles interacting with the CSW potential, as obtained from MD simulations at several temperatures. In all cases, $\lambda = 1.5\sigma$.

the self-diffusion calculated by simulation for a system with N particles in a cubic box of side L , k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T the temperature, $\xi = 2.837298$, and η the shear viscosity. See the supporting information for the self-diffusion coefficient computed in this work for systems with 108 and 1000 atoms and at infinite systems. Note that we use in Eq. (6) the estimated values of η obtained using the CSW intermolecular potential explained in the following subsection.

Fig. 3 shows D^* , as a function of density, at supercritical and subcritical temperatures using a system formed from 1000 CSW particles. As it is expected, values obtained from simulation are slightly higher than those obtained from simulations using 108 atoms. Note that this is the reason for which we do not compare both sets of data in a single plot. Also note that we are using here a logarithmic $D^*T^* - \rho^*$ representation in order to better show the behavior of D^* , as a function of density. Self-diffusion coefficient monotonically decreases with the density. It is interesting to note that there is a change in the curvature of the curves for $\rho^* < 0.2$ as Michels and Trappeniers reported.⁴⁶

B. Shear-viscosity

The second property analyzed is the shear-viscosity. To this end, we have used the Green-Kubo formula given by Eq. (2) which requires to calculate the stress tensor throughout the simulation with enough periodicity to correctly capture the behavior of the ACF, especially in the long-time tail. Although it is recommendable to save the components of the pressure tensor each 5 to 10 fs for continuous intermolecular potentials,⁵⁹ we have checked that in the case of the CSW intermolecular potential it is necessary to use a frequency of 0.5 fs.

From the same simulations carried out to determine the diffusion, it is possible to determine the diagonal (P_{xx} , P_{yy} , P_{zz})

and off-diagonal (P_{xy} , P_{xz} , P_{yz}) components of the pressure tensor. This allows to average the ACF over five pressure components: the three off-diagonal components and the equivalent terms $(P_{xx} - P_{yy})/2$ and $(P_{yy} - P_{zz})/2$.⁶¹

The post analysis to calculate the shear viscosity curve was done using a home-made program. The reported data (averages and uncertainties) correspond to the average of 5 independent runs for each thermodynamic state studied. In each simulation, the value of the viscosity corresponds to the averaged value of $\eta(t)$ from the time at which the plateau is reached until the upper time limit in Eq. (2), fixed at 100 ps in this study. We observed that typically the plateau occurs at ~ 35 ps in the low temperatures and densities regime, approximately, at ~ 20 ps at low temperatures and high densities or vice versa, and at ~ 8 ps in the high temperatures and densities regime. It is interesting to mention that it is possible to estimate each value of η using a different way. One could fit the data using some analytic function, as it is done in Ref [59]. Following this approach, the obtained results are close to those obtained using the criterion established in the last paragraph.

Shear viscosity curves corresponding to systems formed from 108 and 1000 particles interacting through the CSW intermolecular potential with range $\lambda = 1.5\sigma$, at subcritical and supercritical temperatures and densities, are shown in Fig. 4. We have also included the data obtained by Michels and Trappeniers work^{42,43} for comparison reasons. As can be observed, correlation between prediction using the SW and CSW intermolecular potential are in excellent agreement in all cases. Particularly, AAD% $\sim 3\%$ when consider all the simulation values corresponding to the system formed from 108 particles. The simulation data obtained for 108 and 1000 particles are very similar, at a given density, indicating that shear-viscosity is a collective property that it does not depend on the system size. All numerical data are tabulated and are included in the Supplementary Material.

C. Equilibrium properties

Less scarce in the literature are values of equilibrium properties, as internal energy and pressure, and structural properties, as radial distribution function. The reason is that equilibrium properties can be computed easily using Monte Carlo simulations in which the discontinuities of the SW potential are not a problem.

Single-state properties for the CSW potential have been previously investigated by Zerón *et al.*,⁵² however, that study was carried out for restricted temperatures and densities. Taking advantage of the simulations implemented for transport properties with 1000 particles, we have calculated the internal energy, compressibility factor and radial distributions function for all states analyzed in this work in order to compare the available MC data for SW ($\lambda = 1.5\sigma$) fluids to that using MD simulations and the CSW potential.

The compressibility factor, Z , that measures how far is a

FIG. 4. Shear-viscosity, η^* , as a function of density, ρ^* , of systems formed from 108 (crosses) and 1000 particles (filled circles) interacting with the CSW potential at several temperatures. We have also included the results corresponding to a system formed from 108 particles (open circles) interacting with the SW potential at the same temperature.^{42,43} In all cases, $\lambda = 1.5\sigma$.

system from the ideal gas ($Z = 1$), is defined as:

$$Z = \frac{PV}{Nk_B T} = \frac{P^*}{\rho^* T^*} \quad (7)$$

where P is the pressure, V the volume, k_B the Boltzmann constant, and T the temperature of the system. Fig. 5 shows the compressibility factor in a wide range of densities and temperatures for CSW fluids with range $\lambda = 1.5\sigma$. We have also included some MC simulation data taken from the literature. As we can see, there is a good correlation between the estimations obtained from the CSW and SW intermolecular potentials. Particularly, $\text{AAD}\% < 1\%$.

We have also obtained the internal energy, as a function of density, in a wide range of temperatures. Isotherms for the reduced excess internal energy are represented in Fig. 6 for both potentials, SW and CSW, with a range $\lambda = 1.5\sigma$. As can be seen, agreement between both results is excellent in the whole range of temperatures and densities ($\text{AAD}\% \sim 0.3\%$). The numerical data for u^* and Z for the system formed from 1000 CSW particles are tabulated in the Supporting Information.

We also consider some structural properties of the SW fluid. Particularly, we analyze the radial distribution function of the fluid. As a representative example, here we only show three $g(r^*)$ curves at low, intermediate, and high densities at different temperatures. Predictions obtained using the CSW intermolecular potential are compared with MC data for the SW potential of range $\lambda = 1.5\sigma$ taken from the literature.^{13,35} As can notice in Fig. 7, agreement between MC data and MD results obtained in this work is excellent in all cases.

Finally, another structural property directly related to the radial distribution function is the coordination number of the system, N_c , which accounts for the average number of neigh-

FIG. 5. Compressibility factor, Z , as a function of density, at several temperatures. Filled circles are the MD predictions using the CSW potential and open symbols are the MC data of Largo and Solana⁶²(circles), Henderson *et al.*¹³ (squares), Labik *et al.*²⁸ (diamond), Gil-Villegas *et al.*⁶³ (triangle up), and DMD predictions of Michels and Trappeniers⁴² (triangle down) using the SW potential. In all cases, $\lambda = 1.5\sigma$. The continuous curves are guides to the eye.

FIG. 6. Reduced internal energy of excess, $u_{ex}^* = U_{ex}/Nk_B T$, as a function of density, ρ^* , at several temperatures. The meaning of the symbols and curves are the same as in Fig. 5.

bor particles within the well. N_c can be calculated through the following expression:

$$N_c = 4\pi\rho^* \int_1^\lambda g(r^*) r^{*2} dr^* \quad (8)$$

There exist several theoretical models developed in the literature that allow to estimate the coordination number of SW fluids.^{64–68} As can be observed from Fig. 8, agreement between MC data taken from the literature and the results obtained in this work using the CSW intermolecular potential is excellent in all cases ($\text{AAD} \sim 0.4\%$). See Supplementary

Material for the complete set of N_c values calculated in this work.

To recap, the CSW intermolecular potential of Zerón *et al.*⁵² is able to reproduce accurately equilibrium, structural and transport properties of the SW fluid with range $\lambda = 1.5\sigma$ in a wide range of densities and temperatures.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We have performed MD simulations in the NVT ensemble of systems formed from 108 and 1000 particles interacting through the continuous square-well potential with range $\lambda = 1.5\sigma$ in the gas and liquid phases, and in the supercritical region of the phase diagram. Transport properties (shear viscosity and self-diffusion coefficient), as well as equilibrium (internal energy and compressibility factor) and structural properties (radial distribution function and coordination number) have been determined in a wide range of temperatures and pressures. We have compared the results obtained using the combination of molecular dynamics simulations and the continuous version of the square-well potential with MC data of the SW fluid taken from the literature.

The absolute average relative deviation (AAD%) between our results and those taken from the literature found for transport properties is 3.3 and 3 % for self-diffusion coefficient and shear viscosity, respectively. Even better is the case of equilibrium properties, in which the AAD% is below 1%. It is important to recall that we have not observed a trend to systematically subestimate or overestimate data, which corroborated that deviations in predictions are part of the intrinsic uncertainty associated to the simulations.

The main conclusion of this work shows that the continuous version of the SW potential can be used with confidence in molecular dynamics simulations to predict equilibrium, structure, and transport properties of the SW fluid in a wide range of densities and temperatures.

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FIG. 7. Radial distribution function, $g(r^*)$, as a function of reduced distance, $r^* \equiv r/\sigma$, at different densities and temperatures. Open circles represent the MC data using the SW potential taken from the work of Largo *et al.*³⁵ and the open squares from the work of Henderson *et al.*¹³ The continuous line are obtained from MD simulations using the CSW potential. In all cases, $\lambda = 1.5\sigma$.

FIG. 8. Coordination number, as a function of reduced density, ρ^* , along several isotherms. Filled circles are results obtained from MD simulations using the CSW potential, open circles are MC data using the SW potential from Largo and Solana,⁶⁶ and triangles right from Lee *et al.*⁶⁴ In all cases, $\lambda = 1.5 \sigma$.

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